

Carbon balance in an abandoned peat extraction area influenced by spatial heterogeneity and vegetation development

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ABSTRACT

This study was conducted to determine greenhouse gas (GHG) fluxes and assess the carbon cycle of the ecosystem at an abandoned peat extraction site in Lavassaare, Estonia. Two years of measurements from January 2023 to December 2024 using an eddy covariance (EC) technique and closed chamber measurements showed that the site acts as a carbon source. Annual CO₂ emissions were measured as 84 ± 129 g CO₂-C m⁻² y⁻¹ in 2023 and 19 ± 53.2 g CO₂-C m⁻² y⁻¹ in 2024. CH₄ emissions were recorded as 1.28 ± 0.64 g CH₄-C m⁻² y⁻¹ in 2023 and 1.94 ± 0.69 g CH₄-C m⁻² y⁻¹ in 2024. N₂O emissions measured during chamber campaigns ranged from -0.01 to 0.21 nmol m⁻² s⁻¹, with slightly elevated emissions observed in areas dominated by *Betula pendula*, while *Pinus sylvestris* areas exhibited low N₂O fluxes. Closed chamber data revealed significant spatial heterogeneity, with the highest CH₄ emissions in *Phragmites australis* areas. Mutual information (MI) analysis indicated NEE correlated primarily with radiation and energy fluxes, while CH₄ fluxes related to soil water content and temperature. Vegetation type also influenced CH₄ emissions, reflecting plant-facilitated transport in *Phragmites australis* stands. Consistent differences between EC and chamber methods highlighted the importance of spatial heterogeneity and scale. The site is in transition, and favorable conditions, such as a higher water table and continued vegetation recovery, could support a shift to a net carbon sink. Combined EC and chamber methods can provide an enhanced understanding of GHG dynamics and long-term carbon budget assessments of degraded peatlands.

1. Introduction

Peatlands are unique ecosystems that function as one of the most important terrestrial carbon reservoirs, storing about 30 % of the global soil carbon while covering about 3 % of the global land area (Joosten et al., 2016; Leifeld and Menichetti, 2018). These water-saturated ecosystems form over thousands of years under anaerobic conditions, where partially decomposed organic matter accumulates to form peat (Jayasekara et al., 2025). Despite their critical role in regulating global carbon cycles and supporting biodiversity, peatlands have suffered extensive degradation for agriculture, forestry, and peat extraction (Laine et al., 2009). This has turned these ecosystems, which are normally C sinks, into major sources of greenhouse gases (GHGs) and led to severe ecosystem degradation (Yu et al., 2010; Parish et al., 2008; Humpenöder et al., 2020).

Peat extraction, historically carried out for energy production and

horticultural purposes, is a particularly widespread activity in Northern Europe, including Estonia (Karofeld et al., 2017). A critical aspect of peat extraction is the residual peat layer left behind after harvesting (Oestaman et al., 2022). This residual peat layer plays an important role in post-extraction ecosystem dynamics as it influences hydrological conditions, microbial activity, and the potential for vegetation recovery (Kimmel and Mander, 2010). The depth and condition of the remaining peat layer affects whether the site will be a net source of GHG or support carbon sequestration through vegetation regrowth (Keightley et al., 2023). Lavassaare peat-extraction area in southwestern Estonia represents a classical example of a peat-extracted and abandoned site where decades of exploitation have left significant ecological impacts (Järveoja et al., 2016). When extraction finishes, these areas often experience ecological succession shaped by changes in hydrology, soil properties, and the natural colonization of plant species (Andersen et al., 2017). These factors collectively determine whether these areas will be net

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sources or sinks of key GHGs, including carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), and nitrous oxide (N₂O) (Danevčič et al., 2010).

Across the globe, degraded peatlands cover about 50 million hectares which is 0.3 % of Earth's land area and contribute significantly to GHG emissions (Joosten, H., 2016; De Waard et al., 2024). Current estimates of global GHG emissions from degraded peatlands range from 1.30 to 1.91 Gt CO_{2eq} yr⁻¹ (Leifeld and Menichetti, 2018; Leifeld et al., 2019). This corresponds to 2.6 % to 3.8 % of global anthropogenic GHG emissions (Edenhofer O., 2015). Loss of waterlogged conditions accelerates organic matter decomposition, leading to increased CO₂ emissions and, in some cases, higher CH₄ fluxes under certain moisture conditions (Gallego-Sala et al., 2016). Studies show that restoration of degraded peatlands can reduce up to 10 % of global land-use-based carbon emissions, highlighting their important role in climate mitigation strategies (Bonn et al., 2016; Loisel and Gallego-Sala, 2022). In addition, the impact of peatland degradation affects carbon emissions as well as water quality and biodiversity loss (Loisel and Gallego-Sala, 2022). Degraded peatlands are known to be one of the major sources of emissions, with spatial variability in emissions driven by land use, climatic conditions and microbial activity, requiring site-specific management approaches (Günther et al., 2020).

Vegetation recovery on abandoned peatlands is vital in influencing carbon flux dynamics (Purre et al., 2019). Different plant communities, such as mosses, sedges, and shrubs, can have different effects on the balance between carbon sequestration and emissions (Leroy et al., 2019). For example, although *Sphagnum* mosses are generally associated with carbon sequestration, sedges are associated with facilitation of CH₄ transport to the atmosphere via their aerenchyma tissue under waterlogged conditions (Piatkowski et al., 2021; Strack et al., 2006; Ström et al., 2005). Several pioneer species initiate vegetation establishment in the early stages of boreal peatland recovery by colonizing nutrient-poor, waterlogged, and unstable peat surfaces. Among bryophytes, *Marchantia polymorpha* and *Ceratodon purpureus* rapidly establish after disturbances like fire and human activities (Guéné-Nanchen et al., 2022). Vascular plants such as *Betula glandulosa*, *Carex aquatilis*, and *Eriophorum angustifolium* recover quickly through clonal growth or belowground structures, helping to stabilize the substrate and facilitate further succession (Lanta et al., 2004). Understanding these dynamics is important for assessing the role of abandoned peatlands in mitigating climate change. Given the strong influence of vegetation cover on carbon flux dynamics in abandoned peatlands, robust measurement methods are needed to capture these changes at the ecosystem scale accurately. In this context, the eddy covariance (EC) method is a powerful approach that enables continuous and holistic monitoring of CO₂ and CH₄ exchange in heterogeneous landscapes such as peatlands.

The EC method is one of the most widely used techniques for quantifying ecosystem-scale fluxes of GHGs such as CO₂, CH₄, and water vapor (Baldocchi, 2014). The EC method is particularly advantageous for monitoring the influence of hydrological changes and vegetation dynamics on GHG in peatland ecosystems. Unlike point-scale methods such as closed chambers, the EC method provides continuous, real-time data at larger spatial scales, enabling the measurement of ecosystem-level fluxes (Peltola et al., 2015). By directly measuring turbulent gas transfer between the land surface and the atmosphere, EC towers provide a robust way to quantify carbon and energy fluxes of ecosystems in complex structures, including peatlands (Aubinet et al., 2012). This approach relies on high-frequency measurements of vertical wind speed and scalar gas concentrations and enables calculating net ecosystem exchange (NEE) of CO₂ (Baldocchi, 2003). NEE represents the balance between CO₂ uptake via photosynthesis, as gross primary production (GPP), and release through ecosystem respiration (Reco). For instance, recent studies have demonstrated the efficiency of EC in capturing seasonal and annual variability in CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes driven by factors such as water table depth, temperature fluctuations, and plant phenology (Fortuniak et al., 2017; Miao et al., 2012). The method demonstrated ability to integrate fluxes over heterogeneous vegetation

communities makes it invaluable for understanding ecosystem-scale responses to restoration efforts and climate change (Tramontana et al., 2020).

While the EC method has some limitations, such as sensitivity to low turbulence conditions and difficulties in partitioning gas sources and sinks, advances in instrumentation and data processing have significantly improved its accuracy and applicability (Peltola et al., 2021). The use of ancillary metrics, such as footprint models, allows measured fluxes to be aligned with specific areas within the influence of the tower and provides insights into spatial heterogeneity (Metzger et al., 2013). In addition to novel footprint models, which can detect more accurately the flux heterogeneity (Rey-Sanchez et al., 2022), the use of spatial sampling with closed chamber method provides even more precise information about flux variation (Wangari et al., 2022). The closed chamber method is a valuable tool for studying small-scale variations of GHG emissions in specific areas. This method is based on placing the surface or part of the vegetation to be measured in a closed chamber (Luan and Wu, 2014). It is particularly useful for determining gas fluxes such as CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O, which can vary significantly between different vegetation types and soil conditions (Anthony et al., 1995; Pumpanen et al., 2004). Closed chambers are an important tool to complement the EC method by measuring the gas fluxes of smaller-scale ecosystem fragments and to understand GHG heterogeneity within the gas fluxes of the whole ecosystem (Kasak et al., 2022). This method is critical for understanding the role of microhabitats and different land cover within peat ecosystems and for assessing the influence of vegetation on GHG dynamics. Therefore, by combining EC data with closed chamber measurements, this research is closing the gap between ecosystem-scale and local GHG flux dynamics and provides a detailed insight into the biogeochemical processes occurring in abandoned peatlands.

The objectives of this study, in which the EC method and closed chamber method were used together, are as follows; (1) to obtain results on the GHG dynamics and carbon budget of the entire ecosystem after a ten-year abandonment period of a peat extraction area, (2) to understand the effects of different vegetation dominated areas and different land use types on GHG emissions and flux heterogeneity, (3) to assess the environmental drivers that influence GHG dynamics in the abandoned peat extraction area, including energy fluxes, soil moisture, and temperature.

We hypothesized that (i) the abandoned peat extraction site would act as a net carbon source after 10 years of abandonment, (ii) flux heterogeneity would align with differences in vegetation composition, and (iii) differences between EC and chamber measurements would reflect differences in their spatial integration scales.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study site

The Lavassaare peat extraction area covers around 2482 ha within the administrative boundaries of Pärnu County (Fig. 1A). It includes areas located in Lääneranna, North Pärnumaa, and the city of Pärnu. This area, mainly owned by the state and partly managed by the State Forest Management Centre (RMK), is the largest peat extraction area in Estonia (Järveoja et al., 2013). It encompasses the Lavassaare nature conservation area and is situated in Lavassaare settlement, as well as the villages of Õepa and Pitsalu. The 10-year (2015–2024) mean annual air temperature and total precipitation recorded at the nearest meteorological station, located nearest to Lavassaare, Estonia, were approximately 7.7 °C and 675 mm, respectively, based on data provided by the Estonian Environment Agency.

The study site is part of the abandoned peat extraction area but remains next to areas where peat extraction is still active, which may influence the local hydrology. The site remains drained due to legacy drainage ditches established during extraction. Peat depth varies from

Fig. 1. The location of the study site in Estonia is marked with a red square (A), and the location of the EC tower is marked with a red dot (B), used for flux measurements in the study site; the top view of the flux tower taken with drone (C). The wooden platform on which the EC tower is positioned (D) and the transparent tall chamber with portable gas analyzers for closed chamber measurements (E). (Base map: Republic of Estonia Land and Spatial Development Board).

approximately 35 cm in the western part of the footprint to over 4 m in the eastern part. Vegetation at the site is heterogeneous and dominated by *Phragmites australis*, *Betula pendula*, *Pinus sylvestris*, *Eriophorum angustifolium*, and *Triglochin palustris*, reflecting incomplete recolonization and succession after abandonment.

2.2. EC flux tower

The EC flux tower is located at 58° 33' 47.938" N, 24° 22' 7.995" E

(Fig. 1B) and is a part of European Fluxes Database Cluster (EE-Pts). The EC flux tower was positioned within a peatland area that was exhausted in 2014, located near a region where active peat extraction is still ongoing. Fluctuations in CO₂ and water vapor concentrations were measured with an open-path CO₂ and H₂O gas analyzer (LI-7500DS, LICOR Inc., Lincoln, NE, USA). CH₄ concentrations were determined using an open-path CH₄ analyzer (LI-7700, LICOR Inc., Lincoln, NE, USA). Wind speed and direction were measured with a 3-D ultrasonic anemometer (Gill Windmaster Pro). All EC sensors were strategically

located to best represent the study area. Among the microclimatic variables, shortwave and longwave radiation (R_n) were measured with a four-component net radiometer (Hukseflux NR01), while photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) was determined with a quantum sensor (LI-190R, LICOR Inc., Lincoln, NE, USA). Air temperature and relative humidity are measured with a Vaisala HMP155 sensor integrated into the EC system.

Soil parameters were monitored with sensors placed at 5 cm soil depth. Soil temperature and soil water content were determined by Stevens HydraProbe sensors (Stevens Water Monitoring Systems, USA), while soil heat flux was measured by HFP01 heat flux sensors (Hukseflux, Thermal Sensors, Netherlands). The sonic anemometer and gas analyzers (LI-7500DS and LI-7700) collected data at 20 Hz using a data logger (SmartFlux® 3, LICOR Inc., Lincoln, NE, USA).

2.3. EC data processing

The raw EC data were processed and quality-controlled according to the methods outlined by Foken et al. (2004). This processing was conducted using EddyPro software (version 7.0) in express mode (LICOR Bioscience). Which calculated the fluxes of CH_4 , CO_2 , LE, and H over 30-minute intervals. The EddyPro software additionally implemented the following corrections; spectral corrections (Moncrieff et al., 2004, 1997); compensation for density fluctuations (Webb et al., 1980); sonic temperature correction for humidity (Van Dijk et al., 2004); time lag compensation; double rotation for tilt correction; block averaging; and statistical tests (Vickers and Mahrt, 1997).

The footprint was also estimated by TOVI software using Kjun et al. (2004) model to confirm that the measured flux was representative of the plots of interest. Despite all these measures, there were data gaps of 46.6 % for 2023 and 28.2 % for 2024 in CO_2 flux data, and 48.2 % for 2023 and 31.5 % for 2024 in CH_4 flux data as a result of maintenance issues and other unforeseen circumstances as well as data quality control and cleaning processes. We turned to a marginal distribution sampling (MDS) method to address the filling of these gaps (Moffat et al., 2007). Uncertainty estimates presented as \pm values represent differences between gap-filled and original measured datasets and do not account for other sources of uncertainty, such as random measurement error. Upon completing the processing of the dataset, the fluxes have been systematically partitioned into NEE, GPP and Reco by employing the nighttime partitioning method (Reichstein et al., 2005).

2.4. EC data filtering

EddyPro provides quality flag estimations for quality control tests in three classes (0, 1, and 2) (Foken et al., 2004). The EddyPro output results were subsequently filtered and quality controlled using TOVI software ver. 2.8 (LI-COR, NE, USA). During filtering, fluxes with a quality flag of 2 were discarded as they denote the lowest quality data, as well as data below a calculated u^* threshold; a u^* threshold of approximately 0.12 m s^{-1} was applied to exclude periods of insufficient turbulence following Reichstein et al. (2005). The EddyPro software provides a diagnostic output for the LI-7700: the Relative Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI). This indicator can be used to filter out half-hourly values when the instrument is not performing adequately. During data filtering, we applied specific criteria for the flux data, excluding RSSI signal strengths below 90 for CO_2 and below 20 for CH_4 (Polonik et al., 2019; Holl et al., 2020).

2.5. Closed chamber measurements

Chamber measurements were conducted at 35 sampling points spread across the EC footprint to measure CO_2 , CH_4 , and N_2O flux heterogeneity. Measurements were conducted in three campaigns on July 22, August 15, and September 12, 2024, using transparent and white opaque PVC cylindrical chambers (Fig. 1E). Chamber measurements

were conducted between 08:00 - 18:00 under clear-sky conditions with PAR ranging approximately $400 - 1600 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. PAR data were used to contextualize instantaneous chamber NEE measurements. Soil temperature was measured at depths of 5, 10, 20, 30, and 40 cm. Soil water content and soil electrical conductivity were measured at 5 cm depth. All measurements were made during three chamber measurement campaigns. METER Teros 12 sensors were used for measurements at 5 cm depth (temperature, water content, and electrical conductivity), while COMET System U0141 sensors were used for soil temperature at 10, 20, 30, and 40 cm depths. In addition, peat depth measurements were made close to the gas sampling spots (Fig. 2). Sample points were chosen to represent the most dominant plant species and landscape. Soil collars were installed to facilitate the chamber measurements, five collars were placed on bare peat, and five were at the bottom of the old drainage ditch, where plant coverage rarely exceeded 15 %. No bare peat plots were established in the western footprint area, as exposed bare peat surfaces were absent there (Fig. 2). Other collars were installed by the dominant plant species, five collars per species; *Betula pendula* Roth, *Pinus sylvestris* L., and three peatland graminoid species; *Phragmites australis* (Cav.) Trin. ex Steud., *Eriophorum angustifolium* Honck., *Triglochin palustris* L. All the species are commonly found in disturbed areas as they are apophytes and represent similar landscapes.

In addition, we measured residual peat depth at 49 points within the EC-tower flux footprint. Basal-surface altitude at each point was calculated as ground-surface altitude minus the measured peat thickness. We then interpolated the basal altitude over the footprint with co-kriging at 2 m resolution, and generated the final peat-depth raster by subtracting the interpolated basal surface from the ground surface (Fig. 2). In the western sector of the footprint—coincident with the prevailing wind direction—peat thickness falls to 0.35 cm and is absent in ditch bottoms. Thickness increases eastward, exceeding 1 m at the eastern margin of the extraction plot and close to 4 m at the extreme eastern edge of the footprint, near the former railway embankment.

Collars were installed a day before the first measurements. Both chamber types had a surface area of 0.0196 m^2 , with volumes ranging from 0.082 m^3 in areas without tall vegetation to 0.162 m^3 at sampling points with taller plants. After each measurement, chambers were opened to allow exposure to ambient conditions before the next measurement sampling point. The chambers were equipped with two 12 V fans to ensure air mixing and connected via tubing to a portable trace gas analyzer LI-7810 for CO_2 , CH_4 , and LI-7820 for N_2O (LI-COR Bioscience, Lincoln, NE, USA). Each measurement session lasted five minutes, and the final three minutes were used for flux calculations to reduce the influence of initial disturbances. After each chamber deployment, we observed that the concentrations of all three GHGs were initially close to ambient air levels. In cases where a bias was detected, a repetitive measurement was conducted. The analyzer recirculated the air within the chamber at a rate of 0.25 L min^{-1} and recorded CO_2 , CH_4 , and N_2O concentrations at a frequency of 1 Hz.

During the initial quality control, we removed gas concentration values (accounting for <1 % of the collected data) when the analyzer's cavity pressure ($\sim 39 \text{ kPa}$) and cavity temperature ($\sim 55 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) deviated from their operating ranges. The total CO_2 flux measured with the closed opaque chamber at vegetation and bare soil represents the Reco, and the total CO_2 flux measured at the vegetated sampling points by the transparent chamber is defined as the instantaneous NEE between the ecosystem and the atmosphere (Suleau et al., 2011) under the instantaneous PAR values. We calculated GPP when subtracting Reco from NEE.

2.6. Data analysis

Mutual Information (MI) analysis was used to assess the effect of variables on NEE and CH_4 based on 30-minute flux data obtained from EC measurements. MI measures the amount of mutual information between two variables and was favored for its ability to identify both linear

Fig. 2. Footprint map of the eddy covariance (EC) tower located in study site. The colored background represents peat depth (cm), ranging from 30 cm (blue) to over 400 cm (red). The concentric contour lines indicate the cumulative footprint contribution, from 10 % to 80 %. The dots represent vegetation types and land cover within the footprint area, including *Betula pendula*, *Eriophorum angustifolium*, *Phragmites australis*, *Pinus sylvestris*, *Triglochin palustris*, ditches, and areas without vegetation. The EC tower is marked with a red star.

and non-linear relationships. Unlike traditional correlation methods, MI is independent of the direction of the relationship and, therefore, allows exploring the links between variables in a broader context (Shannon, 1948; Kraskov et al., 2004).

The MI analysis used in this study is based on the k nearest neighbor algorithm proposed by Kraskov et al. (2004). All analyses were performed using the Python programming language, and data processing and MI calculations were performed with the Scikit-learn library (Pedregosa et al., 2011). MI scores were used to compare the impact of each variable on NEE and CH₄ fluxes and to identify the most influential factors. MI scores range from 0 (no dependence) to 1 (perfect dependence), with higher scores indicating high and significant dependence.

The data set covering the 2-year period used for this analysis is divided into two all data set and the growing season sub-set. The NEE analysis has included 18 different variables measured by the EC flux tower. These variables are latent heat flux (H), sensible heat flux (LE), net radiation (NETRAD), soil water content (SWC), incoming shortwave radiation (SW_IN), outgoing shortwave radiation (SW_OUT), outgoing longwave radiation (LW_OUT), incoming photosynthetic photon flux density (PPFD_IN), vapor pressure deficit (VPD), soil temperature (TS), air temperature (TA), soil heat flux (SHF), relative humidity (RH), atmospheric pressure (PA), CH₄ flux (FCH₄), incoming longwave radiation (LW_IN), wind speed (WS), and precipitation (PRCP). While 18 variables were used in the MI analysis for CH₄ fluxes in the same way, the FCH₄ independent variable used in the NEE analysis was replaced by NEE in this analysis.

In addition, the Spearman rank correlation test was performed to understand the relationship between GHGs measured by the closed chamber method and other measured point parameters such as soil water content, soil temperature measured at 5 different depths, peat depth, and soil electrical conductivity measured at the time of the closed chamber measurements. Spearman's correlation is a non-parametric test that assesses the strength and direction of monotonic relationships between two continuous variables and is particularly suitable for ecological and environmental data sets that do not satisfy normality assumptions (Spearman, 1987; Schober et al., 2018). The correlation analysis was performed using monthly measurements taken at 35 sampling points and over a three-month period (July, August, September) in 2024. In addition, statistical significance was assessed by calculating p-values, and only correlations with $p < 0.05$ were left in the final visualization. This threshold was set to maintain statistical power while minimizing the possibility of Type I error (Benjamini and Hochberg, 1995). All statistical analyses were performed in Python (pandas, scipy), and the Seaborn library was used for visualizations (Waskom, 2021).

In order to compare the GHGs measured by EC and closed chamber, the Kruskal-Wallis test (Kruskal and Wallis, 1952) was performed to determine whether there was a significant difference between the groups. For the variables for which a significant difference was found due to the Kruskal-Wallis test, the Dunn post-hoc test (Dunn, 1964) was applied to make pairwise comparisons. Dunn's test was applied to evaluate the statistical differences between the ecosystem-wide fluxes of CH₄, Reco, NEE, and GPP obtained from different plant species. Dun's

test was performed using the rank-based z-statistic approach. The measurements for each group were first processed by rank transformation, and then the average rank value of each group was calculated (Dunn, 1964). Statistical analyses were performed using the Python programming language with the scipy.stats library (Virtanen et al., 2020).

To understand the long-term effects of peat-extracted ecosystems on the GHG balance, annual NEE and CH₄ flux values measured with the EC method using the Global Warming Potential (GWP) were considered. For GWP calculations, GWP-28 (CH₄ = 28 CO₂eq) for the 100-year time frame and alternatively SGWP-45 (CH₄ = 45 CO₂eq) were used as recommended in IPCC AR5 (Myhre et al., 2013; Neubauer and Megonigal, 2015). In addition, a GWP of 265 CO₂eq was used for N₂O, following IPCC AR5 recommendations. For 2024 calculations, N₂O fluxes measured using the closed chamber method were also incorporated into the GWP calculations in addition to EC-derived fluxes. However, this introduces some uncertainty as the N₂O measurements only cover a three-month period and are scaled to annual values.

3. Results

3.1. Eddy covariance flux measurements

The daily totals of CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes measured with the EC flux tower, along with key environmental parameters, provide crucial insights into the seasonal dynamics of CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes and their environmental drivers in peat-extracted ecosystems. Over the study period, the mean annual soil temperature was 8.3 °C in 2023. As a result

of the soil temperature measurement probes being out of service due to a technical fault, the data set covers only the first five months of 2024 for soil temperature, so direct comparison between the two years may not provide a fully representative perspective. (Fig. 3A). The mean annual air temperature was 7.3 °C in 2023 and 4.4 °C in 2024 (Fig. 3A). The study site experienced significant seasonal variations, with air temperatures ranging from −26.14 °C to 25.08 °C and soil temperatures fluctuating between −3.92 °C and 22.53 °C (Fig. 3A). The total annual precipitation was 640.3 mm and 554.1 mm, respectively, in 2023 and 2024, showing notable variability across different seasons (Fig. 3C). In addition, the total PPFD shows a clear seasonal pattern, especially during the growing season daily total PPFD values reached 54 μmol m⁻² d⁻¹ in 2023 and 61 μmol m⁻² d⁻¹ in 2024 (Fig. 3B).

The CH₄ and CO₂ flux data show clear temporal and seasonal variations over the study period. CO₂ flux values ranged from a minimum of −348.05 mmol m⁻² d⁻¹ on 20 May 2024 to a maximum of 431.23 mmol m⁻² d⁻¹ on January 16, 2023. The negative flux in May 2024 represents the CO₂ uptake phase, while the positive peak in January 2023 indicates a period of CO₂ release (Fig. 4A).

CH₄ flux values suggest a similar seasonal pattern as CO₂, ranging from −1.24 mmol m⁻² d⁻¹ on February 17, 2024 to 2.82 mmol m⁻² d⁻¹ on August 21, 2024. A clear seasonal trend is observed, with lower CH₄ emissions in winter, especially in February, and a peak in emissions in late summer, especially in August. This shows a general seasonal pattern where CH₄ emissions are higher in warmer months and lower in colder periods (Fig. 4B).

Daily total fluxes of CH₄, NEE, GPP, and Reco were compared between 2023 and 2024 using the Kruskal–Wallis H test to assess

Fig. 3. Temporal variation of daily average soil and air temperature (A), daily total photosynthetic photon flux density (PPFD) (B), and daily total precipitation (C) from January 2023 to December 2024.

Fig. 4. Temporal variation of daily total CO₂ (A) and CH₄ (B) fluxes from January 2023 to December 2024. The top panel shows CO₂ fluxes (mmol m⁻² d⁻¹), and the bottom panel presents CH₄ fluxes (mmol m⁻² d⁻¹).

interannual differences in ecosystem gas exchange (Fig. 5). A non-parametric approach was applied since the data were not normally distributed (Shapiro–Wilk test, $p < 0.05$). Statistically significant differences were observed for CH₄ (Fig. 5A) and NEE (Fig. 5C) ($p < 0.05$), whereas GPP (Fig. 5B) and Reco (Fig. 5D) did not differ significantly between the years.

According to GPP values, the highest sequestration was -112 g C m^{-2} in July 2023, when photosynthetic activity peaked, indicating maximum carbon sequestration in the summer months. The highest GPP value, reflecting limited photosynthetic activity in the winter months, was measured as 5 g C m^{-2} in January 2023. Similarly, the highest Reco value was measured as 111 g C m^{-2} in July 2023, when carbon emissions peaked due to increased respiratory activity in the warmer months. The lowest Reco was recorded as 6 g C m^{-2} in March 2024, indicating

decreased respiratory activity and limited carbon emissions (Fig. 6).

Annual carbon flux data revealed seasonal differences in the ecosystem's carbon sink and source functions. According to monthly total NEE data, the highest uptake was recorded as -42 g C m^{-2} in June 2024, when the ecosystem served as a maximum carbon sink, and this was observed in May, June, and July 2023 and in May, June, July, and August 2024, with NEE remaining negative throughout the summer months, indicating that the ecosystem functioned as a carbon sink during these periods. The highest NEE value was recorded as 23 g C m^{-2} in December 2023, and positive NEE values during the winter months indicated that the ecosystem acted as a carbon source throughout this period (Fig. 6).

The cumulative NEE and CH₄ flux trends show clear interannual variations between 2023 and 2024, reflecting differences in ecosystem

Fig. 5. Boxplots of CH₄ (A), GPP (B), NEE (C), and Reco (D) daily total fluxes (gC m⁻² d⁻¹) for the years 2023 and 2024. Differences between years were tested using the Kruskal–Wallis H test due to non-normal data distribution. Asterisks indicate statistical significance (* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$); “ns” indicates non-significant differences ($p \geq 0.05$).

Fig. 6. Monthly variation of net ecosystem exchange (NEE), gross primary production (GPP), and ecosystem respiration (Reco) from January 2023 to December 2024 in Lavassaare peat-extracted site.

carbon exchange. While cumulative NEE decreased in 2024 (Fig. 7A), indicating a stronger carbon loss phase, cumulative CH₄ flux showed the opposite trend (Fig. 7B), with higher emissions compared to 2023. This contrast suggests that carbon dynamics in the ecosystem followed different paths for CO₂ and CH₄ between the two years. It should be noted that both the peak rates of carbon assimilation and the cumulative net carbon uptake occurred in 2023, consistently indicating that 2023 was the stronger net sink year.

The Lavassaare abandoned peat extraction area, after being abandoned for 10 years, emitted $84 \pm 129 \text{ g CO}_2\text{-C m}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ in 2023 and $19 \pm 53.2 \text{ g CO}_2\text{-C m}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ in 2024, along with $1.28 \pm 0.64 \text{ g CH}_4\text{-C m}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$, $1.94 \pm 0.69 \text{ g CH}_4\text{-C m}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ respectively in 2023 and 2024 (\pm values represent the absolute error, calculated as the absolute difference between gap-filled and non-gap-filled annual summed fluxes, and do not account for other sources of uncertainty such as random errors from instrument noise or turbulence sampling variability.).

3.1.1. Mutual information analysis

In the analyses conducted for NEE, the variables with the highest MI scores in the entire data set were determined as H (0.65), LE (0.51), and NETRAD (0.50) (Fig. 8A). This generally shows that radiative and energy variables drive ecosystem carbon exchange. When focusing on the growing season, H (0.85), NETRAD (0.72), and SW_IN (0.71) have the highest MI scores (Fig. 8B). This shows that the effect of plant photosynthesis and energy inputs on NEE increases during the growing season.

In the MI analysis conducted for CH₄ fluxes, the highest MI scores in the entire data set belong to SWC (0.43), TA (0.34), and TS (0.33) (Fig. 8C). This finding supports that CH₄ exchange is strongly controlled by temperature and humidity. Focusing on the growing season, SWC (0.31), TA (0.22), and TS (0.21) remained the most influential variables

for CH₄ fluxes (Fig. 8D), while NEE showed increased influence from energy fluxes. In addition, the influence of plants themselves on CH₄ dynamics during the growing season should be acknowledged, as vegetation can facilitate CH₄ transport from soils to the atmosphere.

3.2. Closed chamber measurements

GHG fluxes and carbon exchange in Lavassaare varied significantly across different vegetation types and land cover conditions. CH₄ emissions were highest in *Phragmites australis*-dominated areas, with a median flux of $10.77 \text{ nmol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$, while *Eriophorum angustifolium*-dominated areas showed much lower emissions, with a median of $4.15 \text{ nmol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Bare peat areas exhibited near-zero CH₄ flux, with a slight uptake in some cases ($-0.015 \text{ nmol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$). *Triglochin palustris*-dominated areas maintained a moderate and consistent CH₄ emission pattern, with a median of $6.34 \text{ nmol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. *Betula pendula* and *Pinus sylvestris*-dominated areas exhibited negligible emissions, with median values close to zero ($0.10 \text{ nmol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $0.41 \text{ nmol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$) (Fig. 9A).

Dunn test results showed statistically significant differences between CH₄ fluxes measured with the EC method at the ecosystem scale and CH₄ fluxes obtained with the closed chamber method from specific plant species ($p < 0.05$). CH₄ fluxes measured with closed chambers for *Betula pendula* and no plants differed significantly from EC measurements at the ecosystem scale ($p < 0.0001$). Ditch and *Eriophorum angustifolium* sites also showed statistically significant but lower differences compared to the ecosystem as a whole ($p < 0.01$ and $p < 0.05$) (Fig. 9A). For this comparison, chamber flux measurements were grouped by vegetation type and compared to the EC fluxes averaged over the entire ecosystem footprint, acknowledging that chamber measurements reflect localized fluxes while EC captures spatially integrated fluxes.

N₂O fluxes also varied across vegetation types. *Betula pendula*-

Fig. 7. Cumulative changes in NEE (A) and CH₄ (B) fluxes over the year for 2023 are shown in blue lines, and 2024 are shown in green lines.

Fig. 8. MI scores for NEE and CH₄ flux in relation to environmental variables. MI scores were calculated using the full two-year dataset for NEE (A) and CH₄ flux (C), while panels B and D represent MI scores calculated for the growing season data of NEE and CH₄ flux, respectively. Latent heat flux (H), sensible heat flux (LE), net radiation (NETRAD), soil water content (SWC), incoming shortwave radiation (SW_IN), outgoing shortwave radiation (SW_OUT), outgoing longwave radiation (LW_OUT), incoming photosynthetic photon flux density (PPFD_IN), vapor pressure deficit (VPD), soil temperature (TS), air temperature (TA), soil heat flux (SHF), relative humidity (RH), atmospheric pressure (PA), CH₄ flux (FCH4), incoming longwave radiation (LW_IN), wind speed (WS), and precipitation (PRCP).

dominated areas had the highest N₂O emissions, with a median of 0.21 nmol m⁻² s⁻¹. In contrast, *Eriophorum angustifolium*-dominated areas and ditches exhibited moderate emissions, with median values of 0.06 nmol m⁻² s⁻¹ and 0.06 nmol m⁻² s⁻¹, respectively. Bare peat areas showed a mix of uptake and low emissions, with a median flux of 0.015 nmol m⁻² s⁻¹. *Phragmites australis* and *Triglochin palustris*-dominated areas exhibited slightly positive fluxes, with median values of 0.04 nmol m⁻² s⁻¹ and 0.12 nmol m⁻² s⁻¹, respectively. While *Pinus sylvestris*-dominated areas had the lowest emissions (0.05 nmol m⁻² s⁻¹) (Fig. 9B).

NEE, GPP, and Reco, displayed distinct trends among vegetation types. *Betula pendula*-dominated areas exhibited the highest carbon uptake, with a mean NEE of -0.61 μmol m⁻² s⁻¹, while *Pinus sylvestris*-dominated areas also functioned as strong carbon sinks, with a mean NEE of -0.57 μmol m⁻² s⁻¹. GPP was highest in *Betula pendula*-dominated areas, with a mean of -2.88 μmol m⁻² s⁻¹, while Reco peaked in *Pinus sylvestris*-dominated areas, with a mean of 1.96 μmol m⁻² s⁻¹. *Phragmites australis*- and *Eriophorum angustifolium*-dominated areas showed moderate carbon uptake, with mean NEE values of -0.29 μmol m⁻² s⁻¹ and -0.50 μmol m⁻² s⁻¹, respectively. Ditches and bare peat areas had near-neutral carbon exchange, while *Triglochin palustris*-dominated areas and ditches were the only net carbon source, with a mean NEE of 0.08 μmol m⁻² s⁻¹ and 0.28 μmol m⁻² s⁻¹, respectively (Fig. 10).

The analysis results of EC measurements of GPP Reco and NEE and the closed chamber method showed that there were statistically significant differences between EC measurements and Ditch ($p < 0.0001$), *Eriophorum angustifolium* ($p < 0.0001$), No plants ($p < 0.0001$) and *Phragmites australis* ($p < 0.0001$) groups in terms of Reco values. A lower

level of significant difference was observed for *Betula pendula* compared to EC measurements ($p < 0.01$) (Fig. 10).

In the comparisons made for the NEE variable, statistically significant differences were found between EC measurements and Ditch ($p < 0.0001$), *Eriophorum angustifolium* ($p < 0.0001$), No plants ($p < 0.0001$) and *Phragmites australis* ($p < 0.0001$). The *Betula pendula* group showed a statistically lower level of difference compared to EC measurements ($p < 0.05$).

In addition, in the analyses made for GPP, statistically significant differences were observed between eddy measurements and Ditch ($p < 0.0001$), *Eriophorum angustifolium* ($p < 0.0001$), No plants ($p < 0.0001$) and *Phragmites australis* ($p < 0.0001$). For *Betula pendula*, this difference was found to be significant at $p < 0.01$ (Fig. 10).

3.2.1. Spearman correlation analyses

CH₄ flux based on chamber measurements showed a moderate positive correlation with soil water content at 5 cm depth ($\rho = 0.39$, $p < 0.05$), indicating the relationship between wetter soil conditions and CH₄ emissions. A weaker positive correlation was also observed between soil electrical conductivity and CH₄ flux ($\rho = 0.30$, $p < 0.05$). In contrast, peat depth showed a negative correlation with CH₄ flux ($\rho = -0.36$, $p < 0.05$), indicating that deeper peat layers may limit CH₄ production or release (Fig. 11). There were no statistically significant correlations of NEE and N₂O fluxes with measured environmental parameters, suggesting that their variations may be influenced by factors not included in the data set.

Fig. 9. Boxplots showing flux distributions of CH₄ (A) and N₂O (B) across different vegetation types and measurement methods. Boxes indicate interquartile ranges (IQR), horizontal lines within boxes show median values, red dots denote mean values, and whiskers represent data within 1.5 times the IQR. In panel A and B, the "all" category represents flux measurements pooled from all vegetation types combined, while "eddy" (A) represents the flux measurements obtained via the eddy covariance (EC) during the corresponding measurement period using half-hourly flux data. Asterisks in panel A indicate statistically significant differences between EC and closed chamber measurements determined by Dunn's test (* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, **** $p < 0.0001$).

Fig. 10. Mean fluxes of Reco, NEE, and GPP across different vegetation and land types ($\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$). Bars represent mean values, while error bars indicate standard error (SE). Positive values correspond to carbon emissions, whereas negative values indicate carbon uptake. The "eddy" label represents fluxes measured using the EC method during the corresponding measurement period, and the "all" category represents flux measurements pooled from all vegetation types combined. Asterisks indicate statistically significant differences determined by Dunn's test (* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, **** $p < 0.0001$).

3.3. Global warming potential

Annual results suggest that NEE is $84 \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$, and CH₄ emissions are $1.28 \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ in 2023. According to the calculations made using GWP-28, the total GHG budget for 2023 was determined as $119.84 \text{ g CO}_2\text{eq m}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$. Alternatively, when SGWP-45 was used, this value was calculated as $141.60 \text{ g CO}_2\text{eq m}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$. In 2024, NEE was measured as $19 \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$, and CH₄ flux was measured as $0.69 \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$; thus, the annual total GHG budget for GWP-28 was calculated as $64.42 \text{ g CO}_2\text{eq m}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ and for SGWP-45 as $76.15 \text{ g CO}_2\text{eq m}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$. In addition, N₂O

fluxes measured using the closed chamber method were included in the 2024 budget, contributing an additional $26.1 \text{ g CO}_2\text{eq m}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ based on the 100-year GWP. These values reflect the peatland ecosystem's changing GHG dynamics and carbon balance over the years (Table 1).

4. Discussion

4.1. Overview of GHG flux patterns at the ecosystem scale

This study provides an overview of the GHG dynamics of the

Fig. 11. Spearman correlation heatmap showing the relationships between NEE, CH₄, and N₂O fluxes with key environmental variables, including peat depth, soil water content (SWC), soil electrical conductivity (EC), and soil temperature at different depths. Positive correlations are shown in red, while negative correlations are in blue, with color intensity indicating the strength of the correlation. Only statistically significant correlations ($p < 0.05$) are shown.

Table 1

NEE and CH₄ flux based on eddy covariance and N₂O fluxes obtained closed chamber measurement based GHG budget calculated using GWP-28 and SGWP-45 metrics. The GWP-28 and GWP-45 in 2024 also include N₂O data based on the closed chamber campaign and are marked with an asterisk (*) due to large uncertainty.

Year	NEE (gC m ⁻² y ⁻¹)	CH ₄ (gC m ⁻² y ⁻¹)	N ₂ O (gN ₂ O m ⁻² y ⁻¹)	GWP-28 (CO ₂ eq m ⁻² y ⁻¹)	SGWP-45 (CO ₂ eq m ⁻² y ⁻¹)
2023	84	1.28	–	119.84	141.60
2024	19	0.69	0.098	38.32/64.42*	50.05/76.15*

abandoned peat extraction area of Lavassaare, Estonia. Ecosystem-scale and fine-scale GHG fluxes were measured using EC measurements and closed chamber techniques. These findings provide a valuable reference for understanding post-peat extraction sites' complex carbon dynamics and flux heterogeneity. Our site represents a typical example of an abandoned peat extraction area undergoing passive regeneration. Previous studies in Estonia have shown that such sites can act as either net carbon sources or sinks depending on the stage of abandonment, vegetation cover, and water table conditions (Mander et al., 2012; Järveoja et al., 2013). While our study site has been abandoned for approximately a decade, it still exhibits significant spatial heterogeneity in vegetation and peat depth. In comparison, Järveoja et al. (2013) reported similar CH₄ fluxes and variable CO₂ exchange from a drained site in the same region, emphasizing the role of incomplete vegetation cover. These findings support the representativeness of our site and place our flux values in the mid-range of reported values from abandoned peatlands in the region.

EC measurement results disclose that the Lavassaare site acts as a net carbon source during the study period, with annual emissions of 85.28 ± 129.64 gC m⁻² y⁻¹ in 2023 and 20.94 ± 55.04 gC m⁻² y⁻¹ in 2024, where the \pm values represent absolute differences between annual sums before

and after the gap-filling process, and therefore reflect only part of the overall uncertainty as they do not account for other sources such as random measurement errors and footprint heterogeneity. Gap filling provides a reconstruction of continuous time series on a data set containing gaps, while at the same time introducing uncertainty into the final flux estimates (Vekuri et al., 2023). In this study, it was observed that the annual NEE estimates showed a certain sensitivity to the gap-filling process. Before gap-filling, the Lavassaare site appeared as a weak carbon sink, but after applying the MDS method, it was estimated as a weak carbon source. This indicates that the relatively large uncertainty intervals (± 129 g C m⁻² for 2023, ± 50 g C m⁻² for 2024) cover both source and sink conditions, making it difficult to draw definitive conclusions. Furthermore, the high 46.6 % missing data rate for CO₂ in 2023 likely contributed to the wider uncertainty range in the annual NEE. In contrast, the missing data rate decreased to 28.2 % in 2024, and the uncertainty was more limited. Previous studies have shown that MDS can cause systematic biases in annual carbon balance estimates in northern regions (Vekuri et al., 2023). Although we cannot directly confirm such a bias, our results highlight the need to account for methodological uncertainties related to gap-filling and missing data when evaluating the site's carbon budget.

Seasonal trends show that CO₂ uptake peaks during summer, coinciding with increased photosynthetic activity, while emissions increase in winter due to limited photosynthetic activity and suppressed ecosystem respiration (Mamkin et al., 2021). These findings align with recent studies emphasizing the importance of seasonal variations in carbon fluxes in temperate and boreal peatlands (Hendriks et al., 2024; Virkkala et al., 2023). CH₄ fluxes also show strong seasonal variation, reaching a peak in late summer and decreasing to minimum levels in winter. The maximum CH₄ emissions in August 2024 are consistent with previous studies showing that CH₄ emissions are strongly related to soil temperature and water table position (Bridgman et al., 2013; Peacock et al., 2021). The observed suppression of CH₄ emissions in winter may be attributed to frozen soil conditions and persistent snow cover that

limit microbial methanogenesis, as seen in other boreal peatlands (Gažovic et al., 2010; Zhao et al., 2016).

4.2. Environmental drivers on GHG fluxes

The MI analysis results indicate that different environmental factors drive CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes and that these controls vary depending on the growing season. NEE was most strongly affected by H, NETRAD, SW_IN, and PPFD, highlighting the role of radiative energy in regulating CO₂ exchange during the growing season (Schubert et al., 2010). This aligns with past research suggesting radiation is the primary driver of photosynthetic uptake in degraded peat ecosystems (Liu et al., 2019; Nijp et al., 2015). Besides, CH₄ fluxes are mainly controlled by SWC, TA, and TS. CH₄ emissions are more sensitive to soil water content and temperature, suggesting that higher soil and air temperatures and water availability enhance microbial methanogenesis and increase CH₄ release from peat surfaces (Abdalla et al., 2016; Zhang et al., 2022). Unlike CO₂ uptake driven by photosynthesis, methanogenesis does not depend on light, which explains why radiative variables play a minor role in controlling CH₄ fluxes (Lyu et al., 2018). These results also highlight the complex interactions between climatic and ecological factors in determining carbon dynamics in post-extraction peatlands. For instance, increased CO₂ emissions during the winter months may result from increased microbial activity due to freeze-thaw cycles combined with reduced photosynthetic CO₂ uptake (Kurganova et al., 2007). These cycles occur when the soil surface occasionally freezes and thaws during early winter and spring when temperatures fluctuate around 0 °C (Badewa et al., 2022). Thawing of the soil can stimulate microbial respiration for short periods, increasing the release of CO₂ from the surface, thus increasing CO₂ release from the surface, even when vegetation is largely inactive (Zhao et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2014). In this study, although we did not specifically quantify flux responses during individual freeze-thaw events, such processes may have contributed to the elevated winter CO₂ emissions observed.

4.3. Spatial variability and vegetation influence

Closed chamber measurements suggest significant differences in CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O fluxes between areas dominated by different vegetation types, demonstrating the importance of land use and land cover in regulating GHG emissions. Areas dominated by *Phragmites australis* exhibit the highest CH₄ emissions, while areas dominated by *Betula pendula* act as the strongest carbon sinks with the highest GPP and NEE values (Fuchs et al., 2025; Rabbi and Kovács, 2024). These results are consistent with studies showing that vegetation structure influences peat carbon fluxes by modifying substrate availability, microbial community composition, and water table conditions (Keiser et al., 2024; Seward et al., 2020). Although N₂O fluxes were relatively low across the study area, some slight differences were observed between vegetation types. The highest N₂O emissions were recorded in areas dominated by *Betula pendula*, while areas dominated by bare peat and *Phragmites australis* exhibited near zero or slightly negative fluxes. The influence of *Betula* species on soil chemical properties and microbial communities may explain this. Previous studies have shown that peatlands dominated by birch species (e.g., *Betula pubescens*) tend to have higher bacterial and archaeal diversity, which can enhance microbial processes involved in N₂O production (Truu et al., 2020). Therefore, the presence of *Betula pendula* might promote conditions favorable for nitrification and denitrification, leading to slightly elevated N₂O emissions. These results suggest that N₂O emissions depend highly on soil nitrogen availability and microbial processes, as observed in previous studies (Bühmann et al., 2017; Xun et al., 2022). These trends are further supported by the chamber-based flux patterns, which reflected vegetation-specific dynamics across all three gases. For example, strong CO₂ uptake by *Betula pendula* and *Pinus sylvestris* indicated robust photosynthetic activity and carbon sequestration potential, while bare peat and ditch locations

showed near-neutral or source-like behavior in terms of NEE. These flux differences highlight the influence of vegetation type and succession stage on GHG dynamics in recovering peatlands.

4.4. Soil properties and peat depth effects

The positive correlation between CH₄ fluxes and soil water content suggests that anoxic conditions promote methanogenic processes (Song et al., 2021). Water-saturated soil conditions have long been known to provide favorable environments for methane-producing microorganisms, especially in peatlands (Brown et al., 2014). While water table height (WTH) is traditionally used to characterize peatland hydrology, volumetric water content (VWC) can provide additional insight into the soil moisture status above and below the water table, particularly in drained peatlands where the water table is often below the surface (Strack et al., 2004; Turetsky et al., 2014). Therefore, for sites such as Lavassaare, VWC measurements can complement or even substitute for WTH in capturing moisture conditions relevant for methane production. The weaker correlation between soil electrical conductivity and CH₄ flux may be related to ionic density or nutrient availability affecting microbial activity (Nielsen et al., 2023; Walter et al., 2015). The lack of a significant correlation in N₂O fluxes may be related to the generally very low levels of release measured in the study. While peat depth exhibited a clear west-to-east gradient and was negatively correlated with CH₄ fluxes at the plot level, our analysis did not explicitly partition ecosystem-scale fluxes by peat depth. Future analyses, for example by filtering EC fluxes for east- versus west-facing footprints, could help assess whether peat depth heterogeneity influences carbon exchange at the ecosystem scale.

4.5. Plant species traits and gas transport

The five plant species examined in this study exhibit different effects on CH₄ and N₂O gas fluxes due to their different morphological structures and ecological adaptations. *Phragmites australis* is a species that can efficiently transport CH₄ produced in soil under anaerobic conditions to the atmosphere due to its developed aerenchyma, the presence of such gas exchange tissue can explain the observation of high CH₄ releases, especially in water-saturated environments (Van de Berg et al., 2016). *Phragmites australis* can continue emitting CH₄ even throughout winter due to passive transport (Okiti et al., 2024). Similarly, *Triglochin palustris*, which grows in semi-aquatic habitats, may contribute to CH₄ transport with its thin but aerenchyma-containing structure; however, it is likely to exhibit lower CH₄ fluxes as its transport capacity is not as developed as *Phragmites* (Laanbroek, 2010). Both woody species, *Betula pendula* and *Pinus sylvestris* have very low contributions to CH₄ production and transport due to their lack of aerenchyma and generally growing in better-aerated soils. In addition, the oxygenated conditions experienced by these species may promote CH₄ oxidation (Sorrell and Brix, 2013; Ge et al., 2023). Regarding N₂O, microbial denitrification processes around roots, especially in coniferous species such as *Pinus sylvestris*, may be more limited (Florio et al., 2021). In contrast, these processes are likely to be more active in faster-growing herbaceous species (e.g. *Epilobium* and *Triglochin*) (Wang et al., 2019). Therefore, depending on their physiological characteristics and habitats, each species shows different effects on GHG fluxes.

4.6. Methodological considerations

In areas dominated by different plant species, CH₄ fluxes measured by the chamber method were significantly higher than those obtained by the EC method ($p < 0.05$). For CO₂ fluxes, Dunn's test revealed that NEE measured by EC was significantly lower than chamber measurements, especially in areas with dense vegetation ($p < 0.05$). This difference is due to the measurement scale between the methods; the EC method integrates gas fluxes from a large area covering a wide range of

substrates such as *Betula pendula*, *Phragmites australis*, bare peat surfaces, and old drainage ditches. In contrast, the closed chamber method provides small point measurements that reflect localized conditions. Furthermore, the EC system can account for nighttime respiration, showing higher CO₂ emissions at the ecosystem level (Baldocchi, 2003).

These findings highlight the importance of taking methodological differences into account when comparing flux measurements from different techniques. While EC measurements provide a comprehensive and continuous dataset of ecosystem-scale fluxes, chamber measurements provide important information on spatial heterogeneity and fine-scale flux variability (Shahan et al., 2022). The results suggest that there is a clear heterogeneity in GHG fluxes across different vegetation types and land cover conditions. This is particularly evident when comparing closed chamber measurements with EC tower observations. EC measurements provide flux estimates at the ecosystem scale while integrating signals from heterogeneous land cover types in the flux footprint. In contrast, closed chamber measurements capture fine-scale flow variability associated with specific microhabitats (Forbrich et al., 2011).

The observed differences between the two methods emphasize the importance of accounting for spatial heterogeneity flux assessments across ecosystems, including peatlands. We acknowledge that the EC-based net carbon balance integrates fluxes over a heterogeneous footprint, and that we did not perform a detailed area-weighted analysis to evaluate the representativeness of the annual NEE sums reported. This represents a limitation of the current study and highlights the need for future research to incorporate footprint-resolved analyses. Recent studies, such as Rey-Sanchez et al. (2022, 2025), have shown that spatial heterogeneity in CH₄ emissions can significantly influence ecosystem-scale fluxes and that footprint-weighted flux mapping can effectively identify emission hot spots. These approaches combine EC measurements with spatial data (e.g., vegetation, water table, disturbance history) to better capture flux variability across complex landscapes. Such methods were not applied in our study, but their adoption in future work could improve the accuracy and representativeness of net carbon balance assessments in heterogeneous peatland environments. For example, the chamber measurements highlighted the significant contribution to CH₄ emissions of areas dominated by *Phragmites australis*, which may have been underrepresented in EC-derived fluxes due to the spatially averaged effect of footprint (Van de Berg et al., 2016). Similarly, the strong carbon-absorbing function of *Betula pendula*-dominated areas is more clearly resolved in the chamber data, while EC fluxes reflect contributions from mixed vegetation types. However, it needs to be acknowledged that chamber measurements have some limitations when generalizing fluxes at the ecosystem level. The closed chamber method covers small and usually easily accessible areas, which may exclude densely vegetated areas or areas with tall vegetation. This can lead to under- or overestimation of fluxes if such areas have different gas exchange characteristics (Schneider et al., 2009; Günther et al., 2014). Furthermore, chamber measurements are usually made less frequently (e.g., biweekly or monthly), which can lead to short-term variations being missed. The uncertainty in temporal fluctuation can be reduced when using automated chambers but this method is also less suitable for areas with tall vegetation or areas with high water level (Anthony and Silver, 2024). For these reasons, the combined use of chamber and EC methods provides a more integrated understanding of GHG fluxes in heterogeneous landscapes.

4.7. GWP assessment and restoration implications

After a decade of abandonment, the study area functions as a carbon source; CO₂ fluxes fluctuate between a weak source and sink depending on seasonal variations. The CH₄ emissions measured in this study are relatively low compared to some other post-peat extraction sites in Canada reported by Strack & Zuback (2013). These emissions have been attributed to constant water-saturated conditions and dense herbaceous

vegetation facilitating CH₄ transport. In contrast, our study area has low groundwater levels and vegetation with low aerenchyma capacity, limiting CH₄ production and transport, which may explain the low CH₄ emissions (Bridgham et al., 2013). The GWP assessment indicates that although CH₄ has a higher radiative forcing potential than CO₂ (Myhre et al., 2013), its contribution to the overall GWP of the site remains limited due to the low emission rates recorded. The calculated GWP values suggest that the site might approach a transition point where, if suitable environmental conditions remain, it may have the potential to transform from a weak carbon source to a net carbon sink. GWP calculations suggest that CO₂ uptake and CH₄ and N₂O emissions should be considered in assessing the net climate impact of abandoned peatlands. Even if the flux amount is low, N₂O is shown to significantly contribute to the total GHG budget due to its high GWP. This coincides with previous findings showing that abandoned peat-extracted areas can gradually recover their carbon sequestration functions over time, especially if vegetation succession promotes increased CO₂ uptake and maintains hydrological balance (Turetsky et al., 2014; Hemes et al., 2019). Considering these trends, targeted restoration efforts, such as controlled rewetting, could further enhance the site's potential to function as a net carbon sink in the coming decades.

5. Conclusion

This study confirms that the abandoned peat extraction area, where activities ended about ten years ago, remains a net carbon source to the atmosphere. Ecosystem scale CO₂ emission was $85.28 \pm 129.64 \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ in 2023 and $20.94 \pm 55.04 \text{ gC m}^{-2} \text{ y}^{-1}$ in 2024, with clear seasonal variations. The vegetation that has been developed over decade, although being sporadic, contributed to the CO₂ uptake in summer, while non-growing seasons led to substantial CO₂ loss. CH₄ fluxes exhibited strong seasonality, peaking in late summer and reaching their lowest levels in winter as soil temperature decreased rapidly. Chamber measurements highlighted significant spatial variability in GHG fluxes, with *Phragmites australis*-dominated areas showing the highest CH₄ emissions, while *Betula pendula*-dominated areas acted as the strongest carbon sinks but also exhibited slightly elevated N₂O emissions. These patterns reflect differences in plant morphology, soil microclimate, and microbial activity. A comparison between chamber and EC methods further underscored the influence of measurement scale and within-site heterogeneity. While the EC method provided an ecosystem-wide perspective, chamber measurements revealed finer-scale microhabitat variability. Overall, the Lavassaare site remains in a transitional phase regarding its carbon cycle and could shift towards a carbon sink with targeted restoration efforts. Although CH₄ and N₂O emissions are low, they should be considered in long-term management plans due to their high global warming potential. The multi-scale measurement approach used in this study contributed to a comprehensive understanding of the carbon dynamics of post-peat extraction areas.

Data availability

The study site (EE-Pts) is part of the European Fluxes Database Cluster Network, with EC data available at <https://www.europe-fluxdata.eu>. Rest of the data can be obtained upon request from the corresponding author.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Kadir Yildiz: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Isaac Okiti:** Data curation. **Ilona Tamm:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Mihkel Pindus:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Marko Kohv:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Diana Matejuk:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Kuno Kasak:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project

administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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